

Towards a Historiography of Bengali Cinema Or, Everything You Enquired about Herbert Sarkar, but Were Dismissed by the Coffee House Intellectual

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This article attempts an against-the-grain reading of *Herbert* the book (1993) and *Herbert* the film (made in 2005, public release in Kolkata in 2006) and in the process of that reading, tries to establish a methodology for studying the historical trajectory of Bengali cinema, which is a part of the larger socio-economic-political trajectory of Bengali culture in the twentieth century). Nabarun Bhattacharya's *Herbert* (that won Sahitya Academy Award in 1997) is a deeply cinematic novel, going by the admission of Suman Mukhopadhyay (the director of *Herbert*) himself in an interview with Deepa Ganesh published in *The Hindu* on April 7 2006, where he says, “The first reading of the novel evoked cinematic images” (Ganesh, “The Outsider and His City”). Accordingly, the film made by Suman Mukhopadhyay is meta-cinematic; *Herbert* is a movie about movies. Nathan Lee, a film critic, speaks of *Herbert* the film in these terms in *New York Times* on 10 December 2008: “Movies are very much the point of this film: allusions to classic Hollywood and Indian cinema abound”

(Lee, “Storm Advisory: Cyclone of a Life on the Horizon”). In this article we shall see that *Herbert* can tell us a thing or two about Bengali Cinema, and reading of certain motifs from the text-film duo of *Herbert* will lead us into a corresponding study of certain trope from the history of Bengali cinema. The attempt is not just to read *Herbert* as a symbolic/allegorical history of Bengali culture/Cinema in the second half of the twentieth century. Rather, there are simultaneous readings of the crisis of Bengali culture and the communist hegemony and the personal crisis and tragedy of Herbert Sarkar in this article. There have been two English translations of *Herbert* till date, but all references to the novel in this article are made to the original Bengali text, and excerpts from the novel, wherever they occur in this article, are translated by the present writer.

The literary cinematic exchange/transference economy that is at work between *Herbert* the movie and *Herbert* the novel needs to be looked at keeping in mind the nuances of textual transmission, determined by the physicality of a particular medium. Even a certain issue of the little magazine where *Herbert* was first published and the copy of a hard-bound edition of *Herbert* will differ from each other: though both might be carrying the same text, the novel will have different textual expressions and embodiments and sensual forms in each case. However, differences in mediums are as *valid* as the interactions among them. Instead of fetishizing the medium of cinema and the literary medium as two isolated and fortified domains, concretely separated by technology, strategy, registrar and history, we can look at the literary cinematic interaction that is at work in the text-film duo of *Herbert* as transaction of a text across mediums where each medium is coterminous with another, and they together exist within a complex matrix of interrelationship.

Herbert is an extraordinary character. When history hovers over an enchanted Kolkata shrouded in the mist of memory and oblivion, the surreal conditions of coexistence between past and present can be called Herbert Sarkar, the protagonist of the novel and film *Herbert*. *Herbert* is a cryptic history of the degeneration of Bengal in the later half of twentieth century, which is contrasted and compared in the novel with the (once celebrated but now forgotten) literature of nineteenth

century that witnessed Bengal renaissance (if spelt with a small r, we can perhaps do justice to some of its valid critiques). *Herbert* brings to the foreground the relationship between literature and cinema (*Herbert*, in all senses of the term, is a *boi*; the Bengali colloquial word for cinema is *boi* which also means book, and that reflects our deep rooted national desire for narratives as we expect to see a *boi* on screen), and also the connection of cinema to other discourses: like history, for example. The archeology of nineteenth century Bengali culture is a recurrent motif in *Herbert*.

The literature-cinema transaction is not unilateral, it works both ways. The novel by Nabarun Bhattacharya itself evokes cinematic imagery and employs cinematic technique repeatedly. Keith Cohen speaks of novel's deep indebtedness to cinema in the twentieth century, in terms of structure, narrative technique and use of language (79-104). *Herbert* the novel is a case in point. The cinematic technique of montage is integral to the author's design that produces a collage between past and present in this novel. There are multiple quotations from nineteenth century (and early twentieth century) Bengali poetry in this novel in regular intervals; they offer a carefully designed archaicism. They are strategically placed at the beginning of each chapter, and are sometimes placed inside the main body of text, too. They are quotations from obsolete, obscure and quaint sources (most contemporary Bengali readers have not even heard of these writers; some even might suspect them to be fictitious, but all these names of the poets and the lines of the poems are actually historical), hazily identifiable with the age of national awakening of Bengal; archaic and meaningless to the present times, at a first glance they are little more than hieroglyphic elements from a past the contexts of which were different and now they are hard to decipher, at least for the historically amnesiac generations growing up under communist hegemony (since these pre-communistic times constitute an equivalent to what is called *Jahiliyyah* in Islamic world-view; unregenerate and meant to be looked down upon, they preceded the establishment of true and chosen times, which begins in Bengal with the beginning of communist hegemony).

Chapter four of Nabarun Bhattacharya's *Herbert* contains the episode of Binu (the naxalite nephew of Herbert), and it begins with a quotation from Rangalal Bandyopadhyay, “Oi shuno! Oi shuno! Bheriro aaoyaj he Bheriro aaoyaj!” (Hark! Hark! The sound of the Drums of War, dear, the sound of the Drums of War!). This line is actually taken from Rangalal Bandyopadhyay's poem “Shadhinota Hinotay Ke Banchite Chay” (Who Wants to Live Without Freedom!), that became one of the greatest patriotic-revolutionary songs of nineteenth century, and as a great poetry of nationalism, was second only to Vande Mataram in terms of its impact on the people, though now very few Bengalis would be able to remember the entire poem beyond the title. Now, the parallels are too obvious to miss. The trajectory of Naxalite movement shares some uncanny similarities with that of our armed freedom struggle. *Herbert* takes place in a space time location that still has memories (perhaps deeply buried within the unconscious, like the memory of Binu's diary was buried within Herbert's unconscious and it returned to haunt Herbert in his dream) of Bengal renaissance and the revolutionary nationalist movement. The Central Kolkata residence of Herbert – Sahebpara (erstwhile white town) is 20 minutes walk from his residence, we are told in the novel (47) – has been the birthplace of the social, political and cultural awakening of Bengal, something that has been made obscure to the generations living in post-Independence Kolkata. The novel draws our attention to that obscurity while quotations from nineteenth century poetry are placed parallel to the actions that are taking place in contemporary Kolkata. Each quotation, acts like “a giant metaphor, or analogy” to a corresponding event in the novel in a strategy of montage, we can say following Keith Cohen (87). And in this analogy there is a heightened contrast between the coded past glory, and the contemporary pettiness: Herbert is to Bengal renaissance what the times of the house gecko is to the age of the great reptiles.

Unfortunately these quotations find no echo in the film. The film-maker probably could not find a way to represent these elements in an audio-visual medium; they are completely discarded in the movie. Thus Herbert Sarkar is even more historically impoverished in the film than he was in

the novel; apart from the nineteenth century books on ghosts and afterlife, *Herbert* the film does not have any other mention of any old works of Bengali literature. In the novel, these extracts at the beginning of each chapter constitute references to the glorious past of Bengal, as if ancestral voices are heard from afar in a dream. They appear like hieroglyphs: apparently unrelated to the main text, and difficult to comprehend, like rituals whose original meanings are now lost and are uttered by the authorial voice of the writer like esoteric mantras, which begin each chapter of Herbert's life-story. They are actually memories of our national awakening, which is deeply buried beneath the plot in Herbert's narrative. Who reads out these lines in the novel? The omnipresent narrator does. But does Herbert hear them? Certainly he does not. Do these lines influence his life in some way or other? They indeed do. Are these lines a part of the plot? They are, but only in magically foretelling the actions which take place in contemporary Kolkata. It seems the characters are not aware that they are repeating history (that is the inevitable fate of those who forget history), while the writer and the readers are aware of the presentiment offered by these excerpts from nineteenth century poetry. It is a pity that neither these elliptical extracts nor the gap/silence between the lines of these extracts and the events in Herbert's life in Nabarun's text find any cinematic representation in Suman Mukhopadhyay's *Herbert*.

Herbert's father, Lalitkumar (who is called Lalitmohan on page 73 of the novel, no doubt an act of lapse on the part of Nabarun Bhattacharya) has been a failed film-maker while alive; he and his wife continue to witness the events of Herbert's life after they are dead. The entire life-story of Herbert becomes a film that his late father, a ghost, captures in a movie camera (after his mother dies, she joins her husband in this cinematographic experience). Lalitkumar calls Herbert's life a movie, after Herbert has committed suicide, and wants his wife's opinion about whether it will be a hit or a flop (73). The novel ends with an assertion that the life/film of Herbert has been a flop one: there is no picture on the screen, and the only sound that is heard is “cat, bat, water, dog, fish” (80). The film explicitly shows Lalitkumar as the director-cinematographer who keeps filming Herbert's

life, and there are certain parts of the film which make the noise of an unedited rush and appear in the semblance of rush print of projection at the editing table.

The dead parents of Herbert filming his life's narrative

There are references to Eisenstein's *Battleship Potemkin* in the film: when Herbert visits Presidency College where Binu is taking admission, the stairways remind him of the famous Odessa steps from Eisenstein's movie which Herbert happened to watch with his communist elder brother Krishna. This is a meta-cinematic symbol in two different ways. First, Herbert whose life events constitute a film, remembers Eisenstein's movie. Secondly, Eisenstein has been integral to the 'progressive' Bengali understanding of cinema, so the spectators are aware of the revolutionary temperament of the times.

Herbert commits suicide in the beginning of the novel, and then the story of his life leading to this suicide is narrated using the strategy of flashback, and all along the visual imagination of the writer is noticeably cinematic. Different time zones come to coexist within a single frame in the film accordingly. The novel makes the historical-contemporaneous interface into a frequent motif. Different generation share the same screen space, the same frame in the cinematic strategy of the director Suman Mukhopadhyay. All of Herbert's ancestors come together to witness Herbert's cremation. The dead generations constitute a montage to the climax of explosion waiting to happen as Herbert's body will enter the furnace. While the past generations are witnessing and registering

the life story of Herbert, we understand, he too is re-enacting the legacy of his forebears.

The suicide of Herbert Sarkar, which is a direct outcome of his encounter with the rationalists, is full of surreal squalor and wretchedness (something that characterizes the novel as a whole), something that reminds of late nineteenth and early twentieth century Europe's urban decadence. Nabarun Bhattacharya's short story "Steamroller" begins with a quotation from Baudelaire: "Je dis: Vive la Revolution! comme je dirais: Vive la Destruction! Vive la Mort!" (*Halaljhanda* 13). These words of Baudelaire can be translated as follows; "I say: Long Live Revolution! Like I say: Long Live Destruction! Long Live Death!" This theme recurs in Nabarun's works time and again. We can see that death and destruction constitute a montage with revolution in *Herbert* the novel, the atmosphere of which is dominated by an extraordinary gloom. It was written after the 1991 collapse of the Soviet Empire which caused not just emotional and political trauma but financial strain for the writer as he lost his job that he did at a Soviet news agency. There are melancholic references to the collapse of the communist world in *Herbert* (61). After Herbert's death the novel laments: "Herbert is no more. Soviet Union is no more. Hippodrome Circus is no more. Dinu's Restaurant by the side of famous Gosain mansion on Shimla Street is no more" (29). The tone of this novel is so gloomy that it at times leads us into believing that the past of Bengal almost entirely consists of alcoholic, lecherous, selfish, superstitious, petty crooks who are now watching over Herbert in pervert pleasure and accompanying him into his death.

Herbert's death offers a rich multitude of significations. At one level, the cremation of Herbert leading to explosion offers a suitably communistic catharsis. However, the explosion does not signal a return to naxalism. The death of Herbert does not follow a resurrection: he does not return as a ghost like his ancestors. Herbert has just died like Soviet Union, Chairman's China and Charu Majumdar and like them he can not be recalled to life any more. A subversion against the ruling order has indeed occurred and Herbert's dead body has challenged the complacency of the state power. But the explosion takes place through a remnant of the past, not through the promise of a revolutionary future

(which might proverbially belong to socialism). Possibilities of a post-communist aesthetics and politics emerge from Herbert's death. The aesthetic (not in the sense of artistic qualities, but in the original sense of discourses pertaining to bodily sensations; it is from this original sense medical sciences have the antonym anaesthesia) versus logic conflict in *Herbert* is particularly interesting. The compulsions of the physical body we are born with are not malleable to cold reason, which always represents the case of power. Ghosts are no longer commensurate with a world dominated by the immediate urges of the present that is ruled by a vulgar materialism (represented by the rationalists). But paradoxically, ghosts are a material need: our body needs the memory of phylogeny. Human bodies are existentially conditioned to myths. Herbert invents stories of souls because that is a bodily desire to reach out to the dead, while this aesthetic longing of Herbert enters into deep conflict with the logic of a mechanical materialism that is championed by the rationalists. Terry Eagleton, who in recent years entered into heated debates with rationalists like Richard Dawkins and Christopher Hitchens (Eagleton took the side of theology, God and the human need for religion: those who are interested in further reading can study Eagleton's *Reason, Faith and Revolution: Reflections on the God Debate*) observed:

I think McCabe was right to see that the traditional Christian belief is in the resurrection of the body rather than the deeply non-Judaic notion of the immortality of the soul. As Thomas Aquinas might have said, if a renewed form of existence doesn't involve my body it doesn't involve me. He identified people with their bodies – as Wittgenstein did in that remark that if you want an image of the soul you should look at the human body. **Soul-language is just a way of accounting for what makes creative, historical, self-transformative bodies like human ones ontologically distinct from material bodies like CD players and peperclips.** Once one has a sufficiently phenomenological account of the body, such language can drop out of the picture. It's no longer useful in one's battle with the mechanical materialists. (Eagleton and Beaumont 310) (bold letters mine)

Herbert in dialogue with the dead

Herbert is not conscious that his dialogues with the dead are a response to his body's search for signification. From bits and pieces of a tortuous life experience, Herbert builds up myths, resorts to obscure books that deals with ghosts and invents a soul-language that alone can express his ontological crisis. Myths are all that can ever allay the deep wounds his life has sustained. If we read the following excerpt where Terry Eagleton discusses Walter Benjamin's formulation of the significance of the dead body in German baroque tragedy, it becomes evident that Herbert's past was released by his dead body into multiple symbolic readings:

The baroque flays and butchers the living flesh in order to inscribe some allegorical meaning there; since the living body presents itself as an inexpressible symbolic unity, it is only in its brutal undoing, its diffusion into so many torn, reified fragments, that some provisional meaning may be ripped from its organic closure. The body thus achieves its full revelation only as a corpse; it is by death alone that the *Trauerspiel* characters can enter into the realms of allegory, shedding their flesh so that the drama may scavenge for significance among its pieces. In a curious prefigurement of Freudian theory, it is only by dividing the body, grasping it as the decentred site of contradictions between this or that cathected organ, that some potentially redemptive meaning may be released from its delusive *Gestalt*.

Psychoanalysis, like *Trauerspiel* and carnival, is born at the juncture between signifier and somatic, and all three modes explore their strange inversions: organ as signifier, signifier as sensuous practice, desire as the hollowing of the body by language itself. In the *Trauerspiel*, as in *Beyond the Pleasure Principle*, that hollowing is carried to the point of death itself: if for Freud all desire speaks of the utterly unrepresentable silence of death, so for Benjamin the *Trauerspiel* body may speak only when it has been quelled to a corpse. And indeed what is this corpse, that heap of cryptic fragments, that ambiguous image whose image is always elsewhere, if not the very text of the *Trauerspiel* itself, in which meaning and the material letter, voice and writing, presence and absence are at once mutually involved and about to come apart at the seams? (WB 151)

Herbert is a suicide; he is called a martyr in the slogans of his friends when his funeral procession is out, and he is also a pharmakos like the character of Bhogi from Nabarun Bhattacharya's "Bhogi" (the blurb of *Auto O Bhogi* says that explicitly, that Bhogi is another face of Herbert), a novel where a person voluntarily offers himself to be slaughtered as a part of a mysterious cosmic design. Herbert's suicide is the denouement of his being torn between two worlds: the past and the present. Herbert's dynamites are from the past. The past coming back to haunt the present is a very familiar motif in Nabarun Bhattacharya's works. Like Herbert's dynamites, a bullet that remained dormant inside the barrel of a revolver (from the Naxalite period) for 30-35 years accidentally kills a man in Nabarun's short story, "Amar Kono Bhoy Nei To" ("I Don't Have Anything to Fear, Do I?"), collected in his *Sreshtho Golpo*. *Mahanagar@Kolkata*, the third film of Suman Mukhopadhyay is made from three short stories of Nabarun Bhattacharya which include "Amar Kono Bhoy Nei To". Past is a major presence in most of Nabarun's works. And the present times are doomed to repeat the actions of the past in *Herbert*. Herbert's encounter with the rationalists in fact re-enacts one of the most massive and basic phenomenon of twentieth century Bengal: the rationalists versus Herbert conflict that ends in Herbert's suicide reminds us of the nationalism versus communism conflict (among other fields of

social life, it took place in Bengali cinema too), that ended in the tragic destruction of nationalism, which was primordial, mythical, and could not survive the arsenals of intellectually superior reasoning of communist thought.

Simultaneous readings into the trajectory of Bengal's general cultural and political degeneration and the predicament of Herbert Sarkar repeatedly remind us of this adage: those who forget the past are doomed to repeat it. Herbert repeats a past. In the film, the interrogation sequence at police headquarters is cut at specific junctures and flashbacks of Herbert's life begin. For instance the interrogation of Dhanna (Bratya Basu) is followed by flashbacks of Dhanna's past life. Quite significantly, when Krishna (Bimal Chakraborty) is asked by Police officer (Sabyasachi Chakraborty) whether he supports the “terroristic” and “violent” acts of his deceased son, and he replies that state violence was no less terroristic, what follows is a jump cut to the rationalists entering Herbert's house and charging him with fraud. One of the rationalists takes photographs of a hysterical Herbert on the verge of tears, and comments that Stalin would be the perfect remedy for such elements as Herbert, and we immediately associate the rationalists' terror on Herbert (for the crime that he relived some myths and resorted to the ghosts of past) with state violence.

The puritan zealotry with which the rationalists want to destroy Herbert finds its echo in the deep hostilities shown by the cultural bosses of the then Left Front Government in 2006 to the screening of *Herbert* at the Govt owned cinema hall, Nandan (called the 'Art Film Theatre' by its founders which included not just Party apparatchiks, but also the likes of Satyajit Ray), and according to a news report the film was shown only after signature campaigns were run in favour of *Herbert* as a rejoinder to the initial refusal of Nandan authorities to screen this film on the pretext that such a film would send “wrong signals to audiences”, and after running for three weeks (Shamik Bag, “Nandan's Litmus Test”), as another report puts it, the film was abruptly and unceremoniously “shown the door” (“Nandan Frowns on Gay Lover Story”, *The Telegraph*, 20 December 2010). The date on

which *Herbert* was released at Nandan was March 3, 2006 (“An Ordinary Man”, *The Telegraph*, 2 March 2006).

The charges of the rationalists/Cultural bosses (that must have included the then Left Front Government's Chief Minister who personally took an interest in Nandan) against Herbert/*Herbert* and the charges of the intellectual film movement against conventional Bengali cinema share some uncanny commonality. After the intellectual political space in Bengal started being taken over by the communists and their frontal organizations like IPTA, there came an internationalist revolt against nationalist art. Herbert is so odious because he represents a certain essence of traditional, unregenerate Bengali-ness that can not be accommodated into coffee houses and university corridors.

Now, let us look at the left-leaning, progressive reaction against our conventional cinema (that started in late 1940s and continued throughout 1950s), both Satyajit Ray and Ritwik Ghatak being on the forefront of that reaction, though, as we shall see, their attitude to the Bengali cinema that precedes them is not always that of unmixed hostility and is best summed up as ambivalent. If one reads Ray's *Bishoy Cholo-chitro* or *Our Films Their Films*, it becomes clear that he detested early Bengali cinema. The general attitude of apathy and ignoring prevails in Ray's article “Silent Films” written in 1970 that is entirely silent on the silent films made in Bengal and in spite of repeated references to silent film viewing experiences in Kolkata, silent films made in Kolkata find no mention and so it later conveniently features in his “Their Films” section in the collection of his film-related writings published under the title *Our Films Their Films*.

In *Bishoy Cholo-chitro* Satyajit Ray speaks of the horror of his first acquaintance with Bengali cinema in 1927: it was a silent film named *Kal Porinoy* (37). Elsewhere also in his childhood memoir *Jokhon Chhoto Chhilam* he repeats that his first impression of Bengali cinema – the viewing experience of *Kal Porinoy* – was negative, that watching this movie led him to develop a contempt, literally a sneering attitude (*nak shnitkono bhab*) towards Bengali films and that he continued to stay away from Bengali films because of his first experience (30). One may wonder if it was the familiar

'progressive' attitude of bashing early Bengali cinema that led Satyajit to trust so much an immature judgment from his childhood. This film *Kal Porinoy* is very little known today, barring Satyajit's scathing criticism of it; no print survives as it was a Madan production (all of their early films were destroyed in a fire).

Anyway, the present writer's searches reveal that *Kal Porinoy* was the first film of Dhiraj Bhattacharya as a hero (may not be the one to be released first), who went on to become one of the most popular heroes in silent Bengali films and later on a renowned character artist as talkies arrived. In Dhiraj Bhattacharya's memoir *Jokhon Nayok Chhilam* we have detailed descriptions of the making of this film (4-17). It was not an average movie. The director, a certain Mr Ganguly (not the famous Dhiren Ganguly, who is referred to as DG in Dhiraj Bhattacharya's memoir; this Mr Ganguly, always called *Gangulymoshai* by Dhiraj could be P N Ganguly who also directed Durgadas in *Krishnakanter Will*), employed guerrilla strategy of shooting, even before the concept was thought of and the term was coined anywhere in the world. Mr Ganguly himself did not give any name to this practice of shooting on real locations without making the crowd aware that a shooting is going on. Such shooting was low-budget, was done with a very small crew of 3-4 people including the director, and did not procure any permissions from the authorities beforehand. Dhiraj while shooting in the lead role of *Kal Porinoy* was once about to be attacked by a mob who doubted him to be a *chheledhora* i.e., kidnapper of children (because of his make-up which made him look dirty and unkempt). In this film, there were on the location shootings where the crowd did not realize that they were being filmed. One such shot was taken while Dhiraj walked from Sealdah to College Street along the pavement of Harrison Road and the camera was hidden inside a moving car. Dhiraj was accidentally intercepted by a classmate of his who did not realize that a shooting was going on, and what followed was a hilarious event (the friend, after repeated pestering was shocked to be told by Dhiraj that he was going to his tyrant father-in-law's house who had forcibly taken away Dhiraj's wife and son; the friend was away to Allahabad for three months and he could not understand how Dhiraj could be married and

begot a son too in these three months) but it turned out to be an excellent instance of realistic shooting, as it was but natural that the college educated hero would be intercepted by a classmate near College Street. It was a silent film so all the spectators later grasped was absolutely realistic action and not the strange conversation which actually took place. Dhiraj Bhattacharya's memoir gives an interesting description of this incident (16-17).

Dhiraj Bhattacharya

One wonders whether Satyajit Ray watched *Kal Porinoy* carefully. All that Ray seems to remember from *Kal Porinoy* is the rubbing of two pairs of feet in a scene of nuptial night (*Bishoy Cholochochitro* 37). Thankfully, Dhiraj Bhattacharya was no more when Ray was writing this article in 1978 (later published in *Bishoy Cholochochitro*). Because, it would not be the first humiliation that he received at the hands of the makers of the revolutionary and progressive new cinema.

Dhiraj met with some traumatic experience of humiliation at a felicitation programme organized for Satyajit Ray after *Pather Panchali*'s success. Dhiraj was neglected and unceremoniously ignored by the assembled progressive intellectuals. There is a touching narration in Rabi Basu's *Shat Rong* of how Dhiraj was very much impressed by Satyajit's works on the rural details, and Satyajit's realistic treatments, and how he wanted to congratulate Satyajit as an ardent admirer. The humiliation (he was "elbowed out by the rising intellectuals") brought tears to the old man's eyes. It is a temptation to quote the conversation he had with Rabi Basu on that occasion.

"We are now counted among old haggards, aren't we?"

I (Rabi Basu) said to console him, "No, no, why are even you thinking that?"

Dhirajda said, “But they've compelled me to think that. Don't they know that the road on which they are walking with pomp and authority was made smooth with the blood from our bosoms? What days we had! Nobody rented a home to us because we acted in films. If walked on a street, the doors and windows of the houses were closed quickly to protect the honour of the maidens. Had to come to the place of close relative on any occasion at the dead of night lest other invitees got angry to see us and severed relations. Enduring all abuse and derision we nurtured and kept the art of cinema alive. Is this the reward for that?” (1: 22-24)

A deep disgust with the older form of cinema continued to be fostered by the film movement in Kolkata as a hallmark of progressive credentials, as the cultural intellectual academic scenario increasingly came to be dominated by communists and left-liberal intellectuals of various hues. Even such mindless charges were enthusiastically made by Bengali 'progressive' critics which are uncritically reproduced verbatim in an article by Subhajit Chatterjee who teaches Film Studies at Jadavpur University as to why early Bengali films (made in British India under British censorship) did not have depiction of “patriotic terrorism”:

As eminent film critic Mriganka Sekhar Ray noted, “...a feeling of disgust and distaste for the conventional Indian cinema became the arsenal for the film society enthusiasts.” According to this narrative, the general malaise of the system owed largely to the middle class insensitivity towards contemporary socio-political milieu as well as their inability to develop an indigenous 'cinematic' sensibility, thereby encouraging passive emulation of Hollywood products. Reflecting on erstwhile decades of Bengali cinema, another noted film critic Suryo Bandyopadhyay complains, “...even the subject matters selected for making films were of inferior quality. In films such as *Dhooli*, *Achyutkanya* ...or *Bordidi* there was no image of patriotic terrorism, no agitation— in one word anything whatsoever pertaining to Indian politics. Lots of dull, lifeless films full of sentimentality (*nyaka nyaka*) ran in the halls and the middle class used to watch them. And got so engrossed in them that they even

used to forget the Famine [1943] ... (www.jmionline.org)

Most of the charges (and they are clichés) which are uttered against early cinema of Bengal are banal to the point of being ridiculous. For instance, the timid and non-experimental early Bengali film-makers were contrasted with the revolutionary film-makers of China who shot the legendary Long March by continuously traveling with Mao's army in film critic Partha Raha's *Cinemas Itibrittanto* (127). Interestingly, Susan Hayward speaks of the flourish of “nationalistic leftist” cinema in China during 1930s and 40s; the communists promptly effected a closure on such films after seizing power (416-17).

But even when not compared with the revolutionary Chinese film-makers who had a vast country where only bits and parts of it were colonized and who enjoyed a relative degree of freedom in choosing their subjects prior to Mao's take-over, this charge against early Bengali film-makers remains serious: why could not they obtain British government approved raw materials to film the battle of Bagha Jatin on the bank of Buribalam river, or shoot a documentary or two on the bomb-making laboratories at Maniktola, or capture into celluloid the valiant ambush of Binoy Badol Dinesh at Writers', or shoot some reels of Surjo Sen carrying out a raid on Chittagong armoury, or record the moving images of the advances of Subhash Bose's INA at Imphal? And hypothetically, once such films were made, why could not they subsequently devise some suitably revolutionary mechanism to get these films approved by the Censor Board? This is all beyond our understanding. Bengali Theatres often produced seditious plays, but why could not Bengali films? Partha Raha asks (127). Now of course cinema made in Bengal was a medium that depended on the government from start to finish, from procuring raw films to censorship clearance and subsequent release, and to our limited intellect it might appear that theatre required lesser capital and was less troublesome for government in not being visible beyond its immediate audience, but if the 'progressive' intellectuals conveniently found no difference between film and theatre in this particular instance to further their case, we should not argue. It is an entirely different matter that theatricality was one of the main charges

repeatedly made against early Bengali cinema by the 'progressive' intelligentsia, and it was repeatedly argued that early Bengali cinema – prior to the arrival of true, revolutionary, socialist realism inspired cinema – collapsed the difference between film and theatre, and this medium was treated like stage, a charge that Satyajit Ray himself repeats in *Bishoy Cholochochitro* (40); but more of that later.

The result of these attacks on Bengal's cinematic tradition by the (communist party inspired and IPTA legacy-bearing) intellectuals has been disastrous. We were not only taught to ignore our history, but also to detest it. We were impoverished, intellectually and culturally, of the historical continuity of the Indic Bengali civilization, and the already given absence of a Bengali trader class meant that there could be very little resistance to the increasing left-liberal-internationalist hegemony. Our cinema began to lapse into a super-intellectual avant gardism (that in spite of churning out a lot of gibberish and rubbish, one has to admit, gave us some films which continue to yield an intellectual universal appeal to the elite educated urban classes). But quite disastrously, what remains the backbone of any thriving movie industry, that is, popular culture, customs, faith and tradition – they all took a back seat. We were denationalized. Necessity of preserving the past was forgotten. Bankim once lamented that Bengalis were without a history. It can not not have escaped the notice of the imperialists of different hues (Anglo-American-Soviet-Chinese) that it suits everybody's agenda if Bengalis are and will remain a people without history.

Bengal's film history has ever since remained in jeopardy. Recently re-published by Patra Bharati (April 2012), Kalish Mukhopadhyay's magnum opus *Bangla Cholochochitroshilper Itihash 1897-1947* has come with some additional images, many of them being rare photos. One such image on page 115 shows an image of the great actor of yesteryear (and master of comedy) Bhanu Bandyopadhyay (the caption says that it was *Dena Paona*, a 1931 talkie, directed by Premankur Atorthi). Now of course that cannot be the case, as the Bhanu Banerjee we are familiar with was not an actor in 1931 (born in 1920, he was only 11 years old in 1931; the image shows a familiar still of

Bhanu from 1960s). That 1931 film indeed had a Bhanu Bandyopadhyay in its cast, but it had to be someone else, it was another Bhanu Bandyopadhyay.

This image comes with a wrong caption (Kalish Mukhopadhyay 115)

A collage of the images of the senior Bhanu Bandyopadhyay (Kalish Mukhopadhyay 145)

A little research on the part of the present writer reveals that there indeed was another Bhanu Bandyopadhyay, who played the role of a friend of Pahari Sanyal and Pramathesh Barua, called Samir (a minor character with very little dialogues, but he shared ample screen space with the two lead characters) in *Rajat Jayanti*. IMDB (Internet Movie Data Base) page of *Rajat Jayanti* however, makes the same mistake again and hyperlinks the concerned actor's name with the profile of our familiar Bhanu Bandyopadhyay, the comedian. If that database was made by a Bengali after watching the movie, then it is an unfortunate mistake, but by no means an uncharacteristic one (absence of history normally paves way to such confusions: for example, as I am writing this article on 8/8/2012, the current Wikipedia entry on Dhiren Ganguly shows the image of Robin Majumdar, the actor-singer). Anyhow, further studies reveal that film historian Rabi Basu in his *Shat Rong* speaks of a “Bhanu Bandyopadhyay (elder)” in the cast of a double version film of New Theatres (made in both Bengali and Hindi) titled *Obhigyan* – the Hindi version was called *Abhagin* – that was made in 1938 (1: 127). In Kalish Mukhopadhyay's book, on page 145, there is indeed a collage of multiple images of this senior Bhanu Bandyopadhyay. It seems that he was a favourite actor of New Theatres. Dhiraj

Bhattacharya's memoir *Jokhon Nayok Chhilam* also mentions the elder Bhanu Bandyopadhyay (69), who worked in Madan Theatres as well (84).

The above example indicates two things. First, Bankim's well known lament about the Bengalis' lack of history and historical consciousness applies perfectly to the historiography of Bengali cinema. Secondly, absolute lack of support from establishments, institutions, academia and intellectual quarters (all dominated by left-liberal ideology) ensures that whatever little bits of the history of early Bengali cinema survives in the form of anecdotes, catalogues, personal memoirs, popular tabloid features and public relations, they are collected by individuals in mostly journalistic endeavours under the auspice of various magazines and newspapers patronized by common readers. There had never been any systematic writing down of the early history of Bengali film industry. As a result, a critical and scholarly query into early film history has never been undertaken. A serious historiography of Bengali cinema (prior to 1950s) has not been attempted. Quite expectedly, Kalish Mukhopadhyay's book too is journalistic in nature.

It is quite interesting to note that Kalish Mukhopadhyay, editor of the renowned Bengali film and theatre magazine *Rup-Moncho*, was involved with revolutionary nationalist movement and a close follower of Subhash Bose. In fact Kalish Mukhopadhyay started this film magazine in 1939 under the instruction of Subhash Bose himself who felt that such a magazine was needed in Bengal, and who instructed him to take an early retirement from revolutionary politics and devote his full time and energy to this magazine (*Bangla Cholo chitroshilper Iti hash* 370-371).

There were fundamental reasons behind this decision of Subhash Bose. The great leader could not have failed to notice the tremendous import of this new marvel of modernity called cinema for the common people. The star system of cinema is a commonly shared currency of popular recognition and cultural symbolism. Common people love cinema and dote on the stars. A star is a symbol of the aspirations of a community, and in fact plays a huge role in the formation of a culturally coherent community of spectators. Thus Hollywood used its star system as a successful method of cultural

expansion. In Bengal, heroes like Dhiren Ganguly, Durgadas and P C Barua and heroines like Kanan Debi and Chandrabati Debi (and later the likes of Uttam Kumar and Suchitra Sen) became the insignia of popular entertainment provided by cinema and cinema moulded popular culture through its commonly shared pool of narratives and commonly transmitted ideas.

Dhiren Ganguly

Pramathesh Barua and Chandrabati Debi

Durgadas Bandyopadhyay

Cinema, then, is a pivotal process of cultural standardization and is instrumental to the making of a *national language*, a language consisting of certain symbols (stars) and stories and visuals and music which build up a community. Cinema offers the language of cultural communication that gives birth to a collective community that through the commonly shared narratives (and in the Indian case music and lyrics as well) builds up its collective cognition, a commonly shared imagination that shapes popular cultural expressions. Cinema gives birth to a nation. Bengali cinema is one of the prime constituents of the national identity of the Indic Bengali people.

As an aside, one may wonder if the star system is as autocratic and undemocratic as a communist party hierarchy, and the answer will be that there are certain concrete differences. In a communist party (and all party inspired cultural organizations like IPTA etc), an individual who is a boss becomes not a symbol, but a substitute of collective will (Trotsky's concept of substitutionism

immediately coming to mind). A star is no longer a star when people don't consider him one, but the communist boss remains a boss so long as the party does not break into pieces or there is a coup. And early Bengali cinema did not just have stars; even the minor roles were portrayed to perfection by some great character artists. Extraordinary character artists were produced by the stage and cinema of Bengal in those days; ever since the communist take over, a loyal mediocrity enforced by the progressive circles gradually came to rule supreme, eventually canceling out true possibilities of great acting in the name of a partisan collective.

Let us come back to the question of the lost history of Bengali cinema. It is now globally recognized that Hiralal Sen of Kolkata was the first film maker in Indian film industry – whereas Phalke continues to be “credited” with the “making of the first Indian feature film” – as Susan Hayward records in her *Cinema Studies*:

However, if we are to be true to history, then Hiralal Sen is really India's first film-maker. He established the Royal Bioscope Company in Calcutta and filmed plays from the major theatres in that city. A first film of his (dating from 1903) *Alibaba and the Forty Thieves* not only marks Sen out as the first film-maker in India, but, interestingly, also pre-dates by four years France's version of the same story (Pathé's *Ali Baba*, 1907). (Hayward 420)

Hiralal Sen

One significant question is, is there a single mention of Hiralal Sen in the works of Satyajit Ray and Ritwik Ghatak? I failed to find any such mention in Satyajit's *Bishoy Cholochochitro, Our Films Their Films* and Ritwik Ghatak's *Cholochochitro Manush ebong Aro Kichu* (which is a complete collection of his writings about cinema, posthumously published). Most Bengalis themselves have been conveniently ignorant of the fact that Hiralal Sen was the first film-maker not just in Bengal but in India, as is noted by Kalish Mukhopadhyay (375-383), who worked relentlessly to establish this long forgotten fact of history among a people that found a pervert pleasure in its amnesia of its glorious past. Our film history is in a sorry state, and our acquaintance with our past is abysmal, thanks to the relentless efforts of the 'progressives'.

There are certain dominant tropes of the communist version of our cinema history which are repeated to the point of being cliché since the communists took over Bengali intelligentsia: the pre-communistic cinema of the past was generally unregenerate, as opposed to the chosen proletarian art approved by the Party that will one day occupy the world, according to the Marxist telos. It was reactionary, not revolutionary, avant-garde and experimental, like the cinema made by the progressive left-oriented film-makers. It was star-centric, individualist and profit-motivated, as opposed to the true collective art of people's cinema. It was theatrical and full of overacting, as opposed to the anti-professional doctrines of neo-realist cinema which believed with a puritan zealotry in the non-actors' ability to depict the truth of life.

Sadly, like most of the left-liberal clichés, the progressive fetish against professional actors too turns out to be hollow. Satyajit Ray recalls an incident where an admirer of his film (named Mrs Flaherty, who was the wife of renowned director Robert Flaherty) in United States refused to believe that there were professional actors – and not rustic villagers – in *Pather Panchali* (*Our Films Their Films* 55-56). There was an interesting encounter between Ritwik Ghatak and Chhabi Biswas (the former was directing the latter in a film titled *Koto Ojanare* that never got finished and released) where Ritwik began as sceptical of Chhabi's professional brand of acting and after a day's shooting

was over, became a huge admirer and exclaimed: “Baapre, aami kaake obhinoy shekhaate giyechhilaam” (My God, whom I did try to teach acting!) (Das 261).

Ahindra Choudhury happens to be one of the main accused who are counted among the practitioners of the *ancien regime* of an unregenerate theatricality, an oft-raised charge that is repeated in left-leaning critic Amitabha Dasgupta's article, “Nawo Shudhu Chhobi” (202). However, Ahindra was the maker, de facto director and main actor of a silent film produced in Kolkata in 1920, titled *Soul of a Slave*, which makes him one of the earliest pioneers of Bengali film industry, and this film was made even before he made it big on commercial stage. If one follows the conception and production of the film as detailed in his autobiography *Nijere Haraye Khnuji*, one will realize that Ahindra was keenly aware of the differences between film and theatre, even in 1920. Tapan Sinha recollects an event from the shooting of a film based on Sharat Chandra's novel *Datta* in his memoir *Mone Pore*, where Ahindra criticized the director's theatrical style “I have done Rashbehari a thousand times on stage. I know everyone's dialogue by heart. But is this cinema that is happening? This is just stage. I cannot take it anymore” (38). We indeed had a lot of badly made theatrical films in the early days, but we had masters of the craft at the same time. Painting the masters and the abusers in the same brush smacks of vested interests.

Ahindra accepted the offer to direct a Telugu movie titled *Vipranarayan* in 1937 though he did not know the language and all he could do was to look after acting and technicalities as he reminisced in his *Nijere Haraye Khnuji* (2: 130). The film was a success, and shortly after that, he was recognized by the common people in South India when he went to visit modern day Andhra Pradesh (2: 169), he was held in high esteem and was also given a public felicitation (2: 200). South Indian films were shot in Kolkata studios those days. Today while Bengali films are copying South Indian movies and are being made in South Indian studios, one can not help the feeling that it is a vengeance of history on the Bengalis who have failed to celebrate, promote and protect their cultural heritage.

Ahindra Choudhury

Ahindra was a master of the stage, and was given the title Notoshurjo (Sun among the actors) for his performance in *Shontan*, an adaptation from Bankim's *Anandamath*. This play was performed in spite of hostilities from a number of Islamic organizations who had the open support of the then Prime Minister of Bengal Government (led by Muslim League) Khaja Nazimuddin, as Rabi Basu points out, and also reports that Syamaprasad Mukherjee stepped in to ensure that the performance of the play takes place (2: 111). Ahindra was indeed the greatest actor of Bengali stage in those days (closely rivaled by Shishir Bhaduri). But to say that Ahindra did not understand the difference between stage and cinema is a gesture of gross ignorance and characterizes the sweeping left-liberal progressive generalization about the glorious period of early Bengali stage and cinema which they have denigrated to the best of their capacity.

Personalities like Ahindra Choudhury heralded a golden age in early Bengali cinema that culminated in the New Theatres, prior to the 'left-progressive' hegemony in Bengali art and culture. They were characteristically pragmatic about the popular pulse, they were masters of their craft, they nurtured their Bengaliness to the core and spoke truth in their memoir without caring for jargons of left-liberal political correctness. When Bengalis first ventured into moviemaking, the only cinema hall in north Kolkata, Cornwallis Cinema, were under the ownership of the non-Bengalis (Parsee owners Madan Theatres); they made it impossible for films made by Bengalis to be released, as Ahindra Choudhury recalls, and to cope up with this problem, a Bengali-owned playhouse named

Monomohon Theatre promptly changed to a cinema hall to show movies made by Bengalis (2: 60). Dhiraj Bhattacharya records in his memoir *Jokhon Nayok Chhilam* the dirty politics he suffered when he was offered a role as a hero in a Hindi/Urdu film to be made by the Madan Theatres; overnight there was an alliance of the non-Bengalis (mostly Muslims who dominated the fields of direction, music, script and dance) at Madan Theatres who did not want Hindi-Urdu cinema to be invaded by a Bengali hero, and he was unjustly shown the door (166-169). The candid confession of Dhiraj without caring for political correctness is a case in point: the past masters saw reality without the tinged glass of false liberal idealism that would later come to dominate Bengali intelligentsia.

This is not the case that idea of communistic excesses is unfamiliar with Bengalis, particularly since 2006-7 when mass opposition to the ruling Left Front Government began. But liberalism remains such a deep rooted doctrine in Bengali psyche, and the dividing line between left-wing politics and liberal politics is so blurred that that in a recent play of Bratya Basu, titled *Ruddhoshongeeet* Ritwik Ghatak has been portrayed as an arch crusader for artistic freedom against Party's doctrinaire and dogmatic leadership, as a kind of liberal idol. But if one reads the collected non-fictional writings of Ghatak, *Cholochchitro*, *Manush ebong Aro Kichu* the impression one gets is that Ghatak was dogmatic in a charactersitically communistic way. Particularly, the “Principles of Ganantya Sangha” (the Bengal chapter of IPTA) that was penned by Ritwik, is a typical study of Communist Party's propaganda: full of jargons, propagating a cult of intolerance and mindless submission to Party slogans characterize this manifesto (Ghatak 42-55).

Nevertheless, Ritwik Ghatak had occasional praise for Pramathesh Barua, and urged others to study Bengali and Indian cinema in details before getting into Eisenstein and Pudovkin and the histories of Italian, Hungarian and Russian movies; he also comments that “we have been contemptuous about our own surrounding” (73). Ritwik Ghatak is an interesting study in contrasts. In spite of being considered the authority on partition centric movies, he actually lived in a denial of

the partition: instead of analysing it, he always simply thought that it should never have happened, he always refused to “accept” it (290), as if it did not become a reality till he accepted it, and commented that he did not have anything else to say about partition, except that this cutting of Bengal into two parts was a disaster (290). There is a touching melodrama in his attitude, but he fails abjectly to offer an artistic interpretation of partition: but then how could he interpret something that he always lived in denial of? Cultural clashes (just like religion, myth and faith) constituted a blind spot in the class only vision of the communists. His class conscious sympathy for the Muslims of Bangladesh notwithstanding, Ritwik had to go alone to Bangladesh for shooting *Titas Ekti Nodir Nam* as it was insisted by his Bangladeshi producers that his unit for *Titas* could not have in it a single Indian (296). It goes without saying that the tremendous oppression on the Hindus in East Pakistan/Bangladesh has never been a matter of concern for Ritwik. Interestingly, after he returned from Bangladesh, Ritwik Ghatak enthusiastically started addressing his interviewer in Kolkata (not a Muslim) as Mian (307). *Bilet Ferat* (England Returned) of 1921 was a comedy film by Dhiren Ganguly, one of the earliest films made in Bengal, and we think there could have been a *Bangladesh Ferat* with a character like Ritwik as its main protagonist.

Ritwik exhibited an unusual propensity of calling those he disagreed with CIA agents: a film-maker or two who could do something in India already sold themselves off to CIA, he thundered (88). All those who are making blockbuster movies with superior techniques at the investment of big capital are CIA agents too (30), and Delhi is full of CIA agents who do not allow revolutionary movies to be made (326), as Ritwik points out. About fellow film-makers and artists who fail to toe the world revolutionary line, he reserves some choicest abuses: Ritwik calls Bergman a “jochchor” (swindler) because he depicts myth, spirituality, religious symbols and ancient mythical times of the Vikings in his films (instead of showing some proper materialistic and atheist subjects in a suitably communistic outlook), and accuses that Bergman is taking the audience backward, instead of explaining the ancient times away in the terms of the present; Ritwik Ghatak's typically communistic hatred against

Bergman for failing to be suitably materialistic reveals a dogmatist and doctrinaire approach (274-6). Ritwik Ghatak calling Bergman a swindler for celebrating myth can not help reminding us of Herbert being called a swindler by the rationalists. However, the same Ritwik Ghatak later on makes a volte-face and talks animatedly about myth and Indian perspectives because by then the west's emphasis on spirituality became to potent a force not to reckon with, and Ritwik meanwhile becomes fashionably converted to the theories of Carl Gustav Jung, who, he thinks, complements Marxism (299-302). But there is no reason to believe that an attachment to myth might have mitigated his communistic materialism. on another occasion, Ritwik particularly praises the satire on religion in Buñuel's *Viridiana*; Buñuel, by showing that “entire Roman Catholic dogma is bogus”, has become the greatest artist of contemporary times (319).

Form and aesthetics are rooted in cultural consciousness worldwide, and religion is the most important popular culture. The local roots of a film makes it an authentic artefact: in other words, skilful use of myth, religion, spirituality, faith and popular memory is the hallmark of good cinema. There is always plenty of universalism in talks of cinematographic techniques, which are abstract, objective, scientific and are supposedly international, but this universalism is actually a liberal reification of cinema, because cinema attains the status of art only in its cultural specificity, its rootedness, its celebration of the local myth, tradition, popular faith and history. Therefore, Bengali cinema can aspire to the status of art only by becoming a Bengali nationalist art.

Most probably along the line of the Soviets, Ritwik also realized that film-making is a question of “the flourish of the inner soul of the country” and that cinema was not just international but it was a national art too, and called for the “nationalization” of Indian film industry (190); by this term he meant that film industry should be state owned. This is not to argue that communist party and left wing politics have any inherent opposition with a nationality's interests. Worldwide, in most of the countries, left politics has synchronized itself well with national traditions.

However, the left of India (not Indian left, as the communist parties always maintained that they are not Indian communist parties, but communist parties of India) has a long history of anti-national activities and has remained accomplices of British (later Soviet and still later Chinese) imperialism.

Ritwik's dogmatic, doctrinaire and intolerant side was again revealed when he attacked all poetry that was written after Sukanta (though he was ready to make an exception “sometimes for Subhash”) on the pretext of being incomprehensible and reactionary. Sunil Gangopadhyay and Shakti Chattopadhyay were named among those who drank liquor and recited poetry which was nothing but “outcome of constipation” (213).

At one level Ritwik talks of the masses, and at another level, admits that he has mostly failed to connect to them: the insurmountable difference between the radical jargons and reality of popular culture leads to this fallacy. Ritwik laments that the usual thing that always happens with his movies is that the ten penny and six penny seats remain empty while the educated bhadraloks are the only spectators (297). Bengali leftyism has actually been a spectacle of high-brow upper class upper caste people anxiously upholding their difference from the rest of ignorant, superstitious populace. The former stands for culture, while the rest stands for *oposhongshkriti* (bad culture). Ritwik was flabbergasted when a film distributor told him “Mister, make a film like *Kolitirho Kalighat* (Kalighat, Pilgrimage of Kali Yuga), so that the spectators throw fistfuls of coins at the silver screen. We get a penny or two by selling those films” (185).

Because the experimental avant garde art championed by the 'progressives' failed to reach out to the masses, the 'progressives' consoled themselves by concocting a myth that the popular plays and films in Bengal which were commercially successful were artistically retrograde. It is an oft repeated charge that the commercial stage of Kolkata was deeply submerged within the quagmire of *ancien regime*, with no express contact with latest European experimentalism (unless the communists arrived on scene with *Nobanno*). Nothing could be further than the truth. For example, the play *P.W.D* where

Durgadas Bandyopadhyay acted in the main role (first staged in 1940) made use of the *verfremdung* technique of Brecht, where actors drew the audience's attention to the constructed nature of the play. A self-conscious theatricality marked this play while the actors on stage acknowledged themselves as actors. Sudhiranjan Mukhopadhyay's book *Shei Nayok Durgadas* gives an interesting account of the performance of *P.W.D.*. The thespians did not make a cult of Brecht; they did not utter mouthful of theories and did not attempt to run after latest intellectual fashions; they did not even speak of alienation or *verfremdung*; without doing that they could be experimental, and immensely popular too, as they could connect to their masses and share their Bengaliness.

This play used to begin with Durgadas coming on stage with a list of actors, and he summoned them one by one. He called the real names of the actors and they all responded from within the auditorium: they came on to the stage from the spectators' seats. The play's end uses the *verfremdung* strategy again. The actors assume that the play is over and start taking off their costumes and props while still being on the stage and the curtain being still raised; someone starts humming a tune, and someone starts criticizing someone else's acting. In the midst of these, the prompter enters hurriedly with the script, a flute and a torch and exclaims, "what on earth are you people doing? The curtain has not dropped yet." Durgadas' character, Mr Sen inquires why, and he is told that he is yet to deliver his final dialogue. Durgadas: "Is it so? Give me ten rupees. No? Ha ha ha. Well, then P.W.D. Work is over. Good night ladies and gentlemen." Then all the actors sing in chorus: "This earthly world of Maya and illusion is our stage/ the way playmaster Mr Jolodhor makes one up, he plays that role" and the play comes to an end (Sudhiranjan Mukhopadhyay 99). This play attained legendary popularity and was also an example of collective acting, which according to the communist view did not exist prior to *Nobanno*.

We had a commercially successful and artistically innovative tradition of performing arts in Bengal for a long time, but what happens after the left-liberal intelligentsia came to dominate the scenario, was an assault on that tradition. Partition not just deprived us of an immense market, but

threw the domestic economy into deep jeopardy. Bengali cinema gradually became commercially sick, the industry began to dry up as the audiences were not getting the popular entertainment which characterized other prominent industries of India, most notably Hindi and Tamil. We can read Herbert as an allegory of our shrinking cultural production. One dominant theme of popular cinema is that of production and manufacturing of narrative. A look at Mumbai-based Bengali scriptwriter Sachin Bhowmik's *Collected Works* confirms that popular narratives are manufactured out of the already existing elements of popular imagination; popular cinema, in other words destroys the enlightenment derived Romanticism of an original auteur, the liberal humanist fantasy of a visionary film-maker. Popular cinema, like epic and ballad, comes out of the social cultural and political roots of a people. Surapati Marik is a producer who wants to manufacture a hit narrative out of Herbert's dialogues with the dead, as he is able to detect the elements of a popular formula in them. He calls Herbert “choubachhar telapia” (small fish from bath tub), whom he wants to promote and make big (55). The idea stuck to Herbert and it appeared in his suicide note. The small fish of bath tub now goes to the confluence of Ganga and Bay of Bengal, Herbert writes in his suicide note. His suicide was an avenue towards a bigger and unknown world, he hoped. He did not know that he would literally make a blast.

Satyajit Ray sings praise to the formula movie made in Bombay in his book *Bombaier Bombete* from the *Feluda* series. He comes back to the question of formula (for the commercial success of a film) in *Our Films Their Films* (90-91). Satyajit Ray himself celebrated popular imagination in films like *Parash Pathar* with Tulsi Chakraborty (who characterizes stage and cinema acting prior to arrival of leftists). Satyajit succeeded to make great movies because of actors like Chhabi Biswas, he exploited Jatra tradition in *Goopi Gyne Bagha Byne* (a deeply operatic and fantastic movie). He explores the charm, fantasy and adventure of reincarnation in *Sonar Kella*. It is then self-contradictory on Satyajit's part that he continues to whip up 'progressive' clichés against early Bengali cinema for pandering to formulas of popular entertainment (in *Our Films Their Films*

and *Bishoy Cholochochitro*). The film society movement (Satyajit is reputed to be one of its founding fathers) in Bengal has practised a systematic politics of denigrating our past glories. As a typical example, we can take *Cholochochitrer Obhidhan* (Encyclopedia of Cinema) by Dhiman Dasgupta: this book is a characteristic product of film society movement, and is absolutely silent on Bengali cinema prior to Satyajit Ray.

A hatred for Bengal's glorious past, a distaste for the pagan *Jahiliyyah*, the heathendom of Bengali cinema characterized the progressive film-buffs produced by the film societies. Gaston Roberge's (a Jesuit teacher of films based in Kolkata, also one of the leading members of film society movement in Kolkata) *Cinemar Kotha* (Tale of Cinema) is another book that is totally silent on Bengali cinema. The title should have been 'the tale of cinema except Bengal'. It is interesting to note that the foreword to this book is written by Satyajit Ray who only mentions western cinema, European avant garde and the fashionably intellectual film movement as if Bengali cinema does not even exist. And this book was written in Kolkata meant to be read by the Bengalis. The attempt at the denationalization of the Bengalis started by the British was continued by the internationalizing drives of the communist party. International always meant aping the whites, Russian or American or any European ideal, depending on which end of the left-liberal spectrum one find oneself.

Bengali cinema used to be thriving once. It was the first industry outside Hollywood that was called its semblance Tollywood. Madan Studio was renamed Tollywood Studio for a brief period (still later it became Indrapuri Studio), and since then the name stuck. (Dhiraj Bhattacharya 179). As the industry became sick and began to suffer because of poor commerce, Satyajit Ray complained that if a Bengali film was made at a cost of 150000, in nine out of ten cases it would not get its money back (*Our Films Their Films* 39). However, Ray's argument in the same vein that Bengali is understood by only 15% of Indian population, and therefore Bengali films yield poor commerce is hard to swallow. Tamil was understood by even lesser number of people, but that did not prevent them from having a gigantic blockbuster like *Chandralekha* (produced and directed by legendary Tamil film-maker S S

Vasan) in 1948 that was made at a cost of 600,000 USD and was released on 609 screens worldwide, according to the wikipedia article.

Bengali cinema gradually withdrew into an internationalist cocoon, if we are allowed the oxymoron. Films started being made for festivals, while mainstream movies suffered from lack of capital, lack of creative support from the ascendancy class (which was now too enchanted with revolutionary ideals to think about popular cinema), and lack of any social direction as Bengal came in the firm grip of the communist movement. Satyajit himself pioneered in festival-centric moviemaking:

With the second film I grew bolder, and the consequences were less happy. My mistake from a commercial point of view, was to take even bigger liberties with my source material than in *Pateh Panchali* which had at least retained the main contours of the original. As a result, the urban audience which was largely familiar with the plot of *Aparajito* was irritated by the deviations. As for the suburban audience, it was shocked by the portrayal of the mother and son relationship, so sharply at variance with the conventional notion of mutual sweetness and devotion.

Aparajito lost money. It was at this point that the European film festivals came into the picture. The awards won by the two films put a new complexion on the situation, and I realized that a Bengali film-maker did not have to depend on the home market alone. (*Our Films Their Films* 42)

The ascendancy's version of reality finds a dominant place in literature and art, and new realism in Bengali cinema was the dominant world view of the left-leaning middle classes. The ballad traditions of India, and folk conventions were looked down upon. Songs and dances were an anathema for left puritans who were passionate to see their version of reality being depicted on screen. As a result, Bengali intellectual films failed to connect to their masses, and Bengali film industry took its downward turn.

Kanu Bandyopadhyay (Who Played Harihar in *Pather Panchali*) went completely unnoticed and unappreciated in the role of Ramakrishna in the film *Bhagaban Sri Sri Ramkrishna* that released four months after *Pather Panchali* and the film went into oblivion ever since, a fact lamented by noted film historian Rabi Basu who considered the acting of Kanu Bandyopadhyay in the role of Ramakrishna at par with *Pather Panchali*; Basu complained that the film society movement inspired Bengali intellectual spectators did not give this film its due (2: 75).

Popular elements like religion and myth (not to speak of songs and dances) could ensure success of a film. But those elements were totally untouchable for the new regime. In 1958, Satyajit Ray castigates the familiar and well-trodden paths that a director may take to deliver a blockbuster:

There are three familiar and well-trodden path open to him. He can make mythological films, or he can make 'devotional' ones, or he can make 'socials' – preferably melodramas – which must have the adornment of the latest favourite star team. All three must have the usual concomitant of songs and dances and must not be below two and a half hours in length. This last proviso is so rigid, and so firm is the exhibitor's faith in it, that a film which dares to disregard it may never see the light of day.

Needless to say, these formulas do not work every time, but they are the ones that have had the longest and the most lucrative existence. They have evolved out of the producers' deliberate and sustained playing down to a vast body of unsophisticated audience on the simple tradition of the *Jatra*, a form of rural drama whose broad gestures, loud rhetoric and simple emotional patterns have been retained in the films to a degree unimaginable to those not familiar with this unique form of film making. The songs and dances too are a legacy of the theatrical-operatic tradition.

One can imagine a utopian situation where the spread of literacy might have gone hand in hand with an attempt on the part of the producers to come out of the groove and present the film-going public with something more worthwhile than tired reworking of hackneyed old

patterns. But this has not happened and is not likely to happen for some decades yet, unless some chance revolution should bring about the process. So the mythologicals and devotionals will stay and continue to provide the staple fare for the majority of Bengal's film public. What, then, should the serious film maker do? Should he accept the situation and apply himself to the making of *serious* mythologicals and *serious* devotionals, keeping the popular ingredients and clothing them in the semblance of art? This is obviously a way out of the impasse, but it raises an important question: can a serious film maker, working in India, afford to shut his eyes to the reality around him, the reality that is so poignant and so urgently in need of interpretation in terms of the cinema? I do not think so.

For the truly serious, socially conscious film maker, there can be no prolonged withdrawals into fantasy. He must face the challenge of contemporary reality, examine the facts, probe them, sift them and select from them the material to be transformed into the stuff of cinema. (*Our Films Their Films* 40-41)

Let us remember the days when Bengali films were successful, delivered hits in all those intellectually prohibited genres, and the industry was thriving (not just due to the black money flowing from war-contracts). Tapan Sinha joined New Theatres in 1946 as an assistant to the legendary sound recordist Bani Dutta. The first play back machine in India was manufactured in New Theatres studio by Bani Dutta and Mukul Bose, at a time when the rest of India simply used to import these machines from the West; Tapan Sinha recollects fondly in his memoir that some of the best talents from Calcutta University's science college used to join Bengali film industry as technical experts in those days (33). Tapan Sinha further draws our attention to the fact that New Theatres produced some of the best technicians in the Indian film industry (36), most of whom later had to migrate to Bombay while some went to Madras.

Now I shall turn to the memoir of Asit Sen: this book records both the height of Bengali film

industry's glory as well as its most pathetic downturns as the 'progressive' hegemony begins from the 1950s and is complete by the 1970s. By the mid 50s, as Asit Sen recalls in his memoir, Bimal Roy comes to a function in Kolkata and laments the poor technical quality of Bengali films which otherwise definitely came under the category of good cinema (9). Bengali films were unanimously considered to be models by the rest of India, and were reproduced and copied in Bombay and Madras, sometimes unauthorized copying took place too. Shammi Kapoor produced an unauthorized version of Asit Sen's *Deep Jwele Jaai* at a time when Asit Sen himself was directing the Hindi version (titled *Khamoshi*) of his Bengali blockbuster (141-2). Shammi's film, called *Pagla Kahin Ka* reversed the roles of hero and heroine. In this film the mental patient was the protagonist, not the lady doctor, while Shammi spoke all the dialogues which Suchitra mouthed in *Deep Jwele Jai*. This anecdotal history, funny no doubt, proves that Asit Sen, who was reputed to follow the *gharana* of New Theatres could deliver successful films and strike an intellectual balance too (the subject matter makes it sombre; no dance is possible, but wonderful songs and a romance make the day).

Shubhendu Roy (later one of the most renowned Art Directors of Bombay film industry) was running a wooden furniture shop at Lansdowne Road after New Theatres closed down. The shop did not run well and he actually decided to go back to his ancestral village in Pabna district in East Pakistan; Asit Sen and another friend forcibly made him deboard the train to East Pakistan from Sealdah (Sen 18). It was the dawn of the desperately diseased time that would since prevail in the Bengali film industry, the desperate times from which this industry never quite recovered. Asit Sen after delivering some very successful movies, almost all of them strongly woman centric, made *Uttar Phalguni* in 1963 and had to sit idle for a year during which he turned to agriculture after purchasing some farm land in Baruipur in 24 Parganas (26-27, 45, 61).

S. S. Vasan (who made *Chandralekha* in late 1940s which created a history in Indian movie Industry and was in fact the first stepping stone towards the eventual Southern Dominance in Indian

cinema) brought a number of Bengalis to his Gemini Studio in Madras which included the names like Nimai Ghosh and Ajoy Kar and P. K. Sen (now forgotten, he was a legend in film laboratory technology), and Vasan wanted Asit Sen to take over from him the director's mantle of Gemini Studio, as Asit Sen's memoir records (39). Asit Sen refused as he did not want to leave Kolkata. Irony is that later Asit Sen had to shift his base from Bengal to Bombay, as he could not survive in Kolkata. The great exodus of the Bengalis thus is a sorry tale of migration and must not be misread as a glorious and adventurous expansion. Sadly the migrated Bengalis lacked any sense of community and communal bond in sojourn (Sen 34). The legendary crab mentality (“a crab tries to escape the net while others pull him down”) of the Bengalis is mentioned in an anecdote popular in Bombay film circles which Sen recollects, and laments that Bengalis eat the flesh of other Bengalis, which is against the practice of the entire animal kingdom (113-14).

There was a time when Uttam Kumar single-handedly gave this sick industry commercially successful films, most of them having the semblance of blockbusters, as here was an artist who was in constant touch with the national pulse of the Bengali people. Born in 1926, he still carries the memory of the glory of Bengal in art and politics. He was a product of the nationalist age. Little wonder that he mentioned Khudiram Bose and Bagha Jatin as his favourite idols; among the political icons, his only favourites were Subhash Bose and Syamaprasad Mukherjee (Ashishtaru Mukhopadhyay 143).

Nevertheless, the mainstream of Bengali movies continued to be dried up: of capital and of talents. Our best talents no longer joined our industry. Popular culture was to be looked down upon. The law of diminishing returns ensured that our industry will grow more and more anemic in appearance, just like Herbert Sarkar. It is interesting to note that Herbert's lapse into simplistic thoughts and the gradual loss of his poetic capacity run parallel to the retrogressive metamorphosis of Bengali cinema. This lapse notwithstanding, Herbert continues to nurture an inarticulate but organic nostalgia for the old, forgotten times which did not impose alienation. An atmosphere of

longing (*Taan, Maya*) dominates *Herbert*, a longing for the old world, a longing for what has gone away. In the movie, Sepia colour is used to convey a certain nostalgia, while technicolour represents the contemporary.

It reminds of the old world charm of the early school of cinema actors. The dialogue delivery was not casual like the neo realist cinema but had a rhythm in it: it had a core emotional appeal. Songs and dances too held a primitive charm for the common people of our land, but these were an anathema for our bhadrakok ascendancy. The deliberate hatred for every tradition that is native born has been the world-view of a dominant section of Bengali society comprising of collaborator classes.

In Nabarun Bhattacharya's *Herbert*, the leader of the rationalists, Pronob Ghosh, while going away with his team after insulting, Herbert takes the names of some Europeans who claimed to practise occult (who are to be contrasted with Herbert who is a mere “Gopal Bhnar”). This episode is exactly reproduced in the film. It clearly establish the Eurocentric attitude of the rationalists. One process of history that took place in Bengal is that with the arrival of the communist party and its inspired intelligentsia on the scene, the self-hating Eurocentric Bengali collaborator classes now had a fashionably revolutionary way of hating their tradition, culture and past glories, and taking pride in affiliating themselves with the west, which is precisely the case of the Bengali torch-bearers of the International Rationalist movement in *Herbert*.

One interesting question about the rationalists can be raised: why they are not interrogated in the film, which shows elaborate interrogations done by the police involving the friends and family of Herbert. The rationalists could have been quite logically accused of being abettors in Herbert's suicide. Many naxalites and ex-communists as well as some practising leftists increasingly turned to rationalist movement (speaking from my own first hand experience of growing up in Bengal in the 1980s and 1990s) in an overall ambiance of economic determinism, enlightenment rationality and progressivist triumphalism that came to rule Bengal since its intelligentsia and political classes

affiliated themselves with communist movement. The rationalist movement in Bengal, we could say, came to be dominated by a characteristically communistic spirit. There is no denying that Bengal's rationalists constitute a part of the larger left, liberal and progressive paradigm dominating a state that has seen the longest rule by an elected communist regime in the world, and also been the birthplace of naxalism. Many rationalists being naxalite radicals, a reader/viewer of Herbert might feel curious to know their response to the explosion at Herbert's cremation.

Herbert retorts to the rationalists

In many ways the Bengali continuum of compradorship reveals itself in the trajectory of Bengali cinema, and the life-movie of Herbert. Satyajit Ray accuses that most of the early Bengali cinema used to copy Hollywood, and even Pramathesh Barua's films had an overt appearance of hybridity, instead of pure Bengaliness (*Bishoy Cholo chitro* 39-40). There is substantial truth in this statement. Bengalis have long been captivated by the fascinating power of the west. The photo album of failed director-producer Lalitkumar Sarkar is a case in point in Nabarun's *Herbert* (20). It contained the colour images of the who's who from Hollywood. The very name of Herbert is borrowed from the west: it signifies a submission to the charm of the west. Herbert's father who made movies in Tollygunge was an ardent admirer of Hollywood movies. The name of Herbert derived from the name of Leslie Howard, as Lalitkumar thought that Herbert resembled that particular Hollywood actor (21).

Herbert was given a worn-out moth-eaten Ulster coat that originally belonged to his uncle, Girishkumar (27). Herbert wore that and stood in front of the mirror and uttered “Cat, Bat, Water, Dog, Fish” (47). There is a post-colonial angle in “Cat Bat Water Dog Fish”; these words may be the first line of any English primer. These words signify the charms of English for Herbert who otherwise does not know the language. The angel's statue at a Shahebpara curio shop, the fairy outside the window on the night of Herbert's suicide, the Ulster coat are core symbols of Kolkata's fascination with the its former rulers from the western hemisphere. Herbert takes a regular walk everyday during winter in his memorable attire of the Ulster coat (called “Olestar” in Bengali), and Suman Mukhopadhyay's visual imagination of these strolls is brilliant, though his Herbert wears a simple overcoat. Herbert stands apart from the crowd. His walks along the streets of Shahebpara constitute a melancholy signifier of a trapped past that is still powerless to be redeemed. While he takes solitary strolls in the white town of Kolkata, the janitors and ayahs suspect that Herbert may have European blood in his veins (47). In the film, Herbert in his black overcoat also foreshadows his own death, and I am reminded of Terry Eagleton's lines: “Peerlessly self-composed, resisting the dismembered crowd, the *flâneur* moves majestically against that historical grain that would decompose his body into an alien meaning, reduce his numinous presence to an allegory of loss” (*Walter Benjamin* 154).

There is a certain human difficulty in living without myths. The second film of Suman Mukhopadhyay, *Chaturanga*, based on Tagore's eponymous novel, traces a post-enlightenment, post-rationalist journey of two Presidency College educated friends, who find solace in Hinduism and become disciples of a spiritual Guru. Herbert never needed a Guru to access myths. A divine simpleton, he can directly approach certain raw and primordial spaces within human desire, in the unrepressed gesture of communicating with the dead. Herbert signals the arrival of post-enlightenment, post-rational, post-modern and most importantly post-communist consciousness. Significantly, *Herbert* is no dissident manifesto of a Foucauldian madman: saying so would be a

misreading of Herbert's predicament. The author Nabarun Bhattacharya tried (and quite successfully did so) to depict the classical tragedy of a circumstantially trapped protagonist, who needs to invent myths to make sense of the world around him, and just when he is capable of making sense of the world through myths, the world can no longer make any sense out of him, and can only torture him for being recalcitrantly resistant to the ways of the rational world. The film of Suman Mukhopadhyay dextrously transacts this tragedy to celluloid.

Shubhashish Mukhopadhyay (who plays Herbert) in conversation with director Suman Mukhopadhyay

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